

TEXTURAL ANALYSIS OF A TWO-DIMENSIONAL METAL-ORGANIC FRAMEWORK CATENA[BIS (μ_2 - (+) -TARTRATE) -DIAQUA-DI- ZINC (II) TRIHYDRATE] OBTAINED FROM NITROGEN ADSORPTION.

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Nitrogen adsorption of the compound was carried out. The sample was synthesized using the solvothermal method. Its crystalline structure was confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD), and its purity was determined to be 99.5% through elemental analysis. The compound was used in the form of a crystalline powder. To remove adsorbed gases and moisture, the sample was degassed at a temperature of 120°C under a vacuum of $<10^{-3}$ Torr for 12 hours. Prior to adsorption measurements, the sample was purified with high-purity nitrogen. The mass of the degassed sample used for adsorption measurements was 0.100 g. Nitrogen (N_2) gas with a purity of 99.999% was used as the adsorbate. Before use, the gas was dried using molecular sieves. The adsorption isotherm was measured volumetrically using an Autosorb iQ gas sorption analyzer. Dead volumes in the adsorbent were calibrated with helium. The adsorption isotherm of nitrogen on catena[bis (μ_2 - (+) -tartrate) -diaqua-di-zinc (II) trihydrate] was measured by the volumetric method using the Autosorb iQ gas sorption analyzer. The pressure was measured with an accuracy of $\pm 0.01\%$, and the temperature was maintained at 77 K using liquid nitrogen [1].

Table 1. Textural properties based on nitrogen adsorption of catena-[bis (1,4-tartrate) cobalt (II) hydrate]

$S_{BET}, m^2/g$	484,51
t-Plot Micropore Area, m^2/g	112,45
t-Plot external surface area, m^2/g	246,12
Cumulative surface area of mesopores (BJH), m^2/g	309,41
t-Plot micropore volume, cm^3/g	0,46
Mesopores cumulative volume, cm^3/g	0,98
Maximum pore volume (HK), cm^3/g	1,45
Average pore diameter (4V/A by BET), \AA	120,3
Median pore width, \AA	26,4
Average pore hydraulic radius (V/A by MP method), \AA	11,23

The time to reach equilibrium varied from 30 minutes to 2 hours, depending on the pressure point. To ensure the accuracy of the results, the isotherm measurement was repeated with the same sample, followed by a new sample. The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm for samples at 77 K is illustrated in Figure 1 [2]. The isotherm belongs to type V according to IUPAC, followed by a small amount of capillary condensation, forming an H3 hysteresis loop (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Nitrogen adsorption isotherm of catena[bis (μ - (+) -tartrato) -diaqua-diruthenium (II) trihydrate]

The BET surface analysis was conducted using nitrogen at a temperature of 77 K ($P/P_0 = 0.05$ and 0.30), yielding a surface area of $484.51 m^2/g$ and a monolayer capacity of $1.08 mmol/g$. The NLDFT method was applied to a cylindrical pore model with a surface tension of $8.9 mN/m$ for liquid nitrogen

(see Fig. 2). The pore size distribution revealed mesopores with an average diameter of 2.64 nm and a total pore volume of 0.98 cm³/g (see Table 1). The BET surface area, pore size distribution, and total pore volume indicate that the adsorbent is predominantly mesoporous, which suggests its effectiveness for applications in catalysis and gas storage.

Figure 2. Volume histogram of catena[bis(μ²- (+)-tartrate)-diaqua-di-ruthenium (II) trihydrate].

References:

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